

Membership of the Policy Working Group that was convened in January 2020 to agree the scope of the review of evidence for Gonadotropin Releasing Hormone Analogues, and Cross Sex Hormones, for Children and Young People with Gender Dysphoria

1	Dr Hilary Cass	Chair; Past President of Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health
2	S40	Consultant in Paediatric Endocrinology
3		Senior Public Health Adviser
4		Consultant in Paediatric and Adolescent Endocrinology -
5		Professor in Primary Care Research
6		Clinical Psychologist
7		Patient and public voice representative
8		Consultant Clinical Psychologist
9		Consultant Community Paediatrician
10		Professor of Clinical and Biomedical Ethics
11		Professor of Clinical Psychology Research
12		National Head of Safeguarding, NHS England
13		Professor of Evidence-Based Medicine
14		Patient and public voice representative
15		Consultant in Paediatric Endocrinology
16		Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist
17		Patient and public voice representative
18		Clinical Policy Fellow, NHS England (secretariat)
19		Senior Professional Adviser, NHS Wales